

Clusters of Executive Need: Qualitative Review

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Background: Opportunity exists to do a qualitative review of executive need by quota sample. The Dutch lifestyle model by *Arts en Leefstijl* has six clusters: nutrition, connection, substances, exercise, relaxation, and sleep.¹ Maslow's hierarchy of needs model has five clusters: physiological, safety, love, esteem, and self-actualization.² It is unclear how lifestyle differs from life and how it differs from self-care. Broader context of executive need is legislative - and judiciary need.³

Methods: Qualitative review by one reviewer by the quota sample: four clusters of executive need. Four was a random choice.

Results: The initial data was: feed (nutrition and imagery), hygiene (cleaning and letting go), gadgets, and rest (sleep and lion-in-the-shadow). The final data was: feed (nutrition and imagery), structural engineering, and rest (sleep and calibration). Gadgets meant structural engineering and lion-in-the-shadow meant calibration. Hygiene was no separate cluster.

Conclusions: The result is very much alike the lifestyle model by *Arts en Leefstijl*. Besides some renaming (e.g. connection to imagery, relaxation to calibration) and some relocation (e.g. substances and exercise sorted under structural engineering), fulfilment is deleted from being an example of connection. Fulfilment is legislative need. It sets the bar for executive need, e.g. to go swimming the patient's executive need is to put on sunscreen. Fulfilment might be a synonym of Maslow's self-actualization, which appears at the top of the hierarchy of needs. In the self-care model by SCARU, hygiene is a separate cluster.⁴

References

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